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A Theological Reflection on the Yoruba Cultural Understanding of *Ìgbàyí láàárò* and its Relevance to the Christian's Understanding of the Passage of Time

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Abstract

This paper discusses the Yoruba cultural expression *Ìgbàyí láàárò* and its relevance to a Christian understanding of the passage of time. While humans often experience frustration or discouragement when favours or opportunities arrive late, the Bible presents divine timing as purposeful, meaningful, and always effective. The work adopts a qualitative, analytical, and theological approach as well as scriptural review and exegesis of passages on timing alongside the cultural understanding that *Ìgbàyí láàárò* depicts. It employs comparative analysis to relate biblical concepts of *chronos* (measured time) and *kairos* (opportune time) to Yoruba notions of *ìgbà* and *àkókò/àsìkò*. The study demonstrates that integrating indigenous cultural insights with scriptural reflection can deepen Christian understanding of timing, responsibility, and responsiveness. Ultimately, *Ìgbàyí láàárò* functions as a bridge between cultural experience and theological reflection, highlighting the importance of discerning the right moment for action and cultivating trust in God's timing. The findings reveal that the concept of passage of time differs, but timing in Scripture is more than a measure of hours or days; it carries profound moral and spiritual significance. Upon recommendations, the author concludes that a proper understanding of timing, as seen in both cultural practice and biblical teaching, provides a fuller way of understanding human actions and divine activity.

Thesis Statement

This paper gives a theological reflection of the Yoruba cultural understanding of *ìgbàyí láàárò* and its relevance to the Christian's understanding of the passage of time. It explores how a Christian can apply the concept of *ìgbàyí láàárò* to the Bible and the spiritual lessons that can be drawn from the application.

1.0 Introduction

Different scholars have explained time in different ways, showing that it is not just about clocks and calendars but also about how people experience life. In African philosophy, John S. Mbiti explains that time is mainly focused on the present and the past. According to him, people understand time through events (which have occurred or are taking place) rather than through numbers or strict schedules. This means time is meaningful when something is taking place, such as social activities, rituals, or daily life.¹ This idea helps explain why, in many African settings, time is more flexible and based on events than on exact clock time.

In philosophy, Presentism suggests another way to understand time. This view says that only the present is real, the past is gone, and the future has not yet happened. This means that what truly matters is what is happening now, because that is the only moment that exists.² This perspective helps see why people often focus on current situations and immediate experiences rather than future plans.

Another idea of time comes from the phenomenological view of time in the work of Martin Heidegger. According to him, we understand time through memory, being aware of the present and anticipating the future, rather than through clocks or calendars.³ This means that time is lived and experienced, not just counted. The past, present, and future are interconnected; the past shapes how we act in the present, and our sense of the future guides decisions. For Heidegger, time is inseparable from being; it is through our experience of time that we understand ourselves, our actions, and our place in the world.

Ìgbàyi láàárò is a Yoruba phrase that translates to "(at) this time of the morning". The phrase on its own is used as a response to a late task being done. It is beyond telling the hearer that they are late. It involves a conscious acknowledgement that the most productive time frame for

¹Religion Essay 3: Time (Mbiti)," Studocu, <https://www.studocu.com/en-us/document/john-jay-college-of-criminal-justice/eastern-religions/religion-essay-3-time-mbiti/2002939>

² "Presentism," *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, <https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/presentism/>

³ Heidegger," *Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, <https://iep.utm.edu/heidegger/>

a task to be performed has passed. There are several ways Yoruba speakers might complete the phrase as it can be context dependent.

This study however, gives three ways the proverbial phrase might be completed. First, *Ìgbàyí láàárò l'arúgbó n kò ebè* which translates to (at) this time of the morning is an old person making heaps. *L'arúgbó* is a contracted form of *li arúgbó* where *li* or *ni*, depending on the dialect, is the preposition. *Arúgbó* is a gender neutral term for an old person, especially one who is very old, even to the point of dependence on a younger person. This should be differentiated from *àgbàlagbà* which refers to an old person, but one who is still agile enough. People in their 60s, 70s, or even 80s may be called *àgbàlagbà*, especially if they are still mobile or fairly agile. Older people of 90 and above would more appropriately fit the description *arúgbó*. *Ì* denotes present continuous tense. The verb *kò* (roughly meaning to build) here collocates with the noun *ebè* (which means heap) to express the agrarian act of making or building heaps on a farm. Since ancient Yoruba people were primarily agrarian, making heaps was a common farm practice for planting things like yams, cocoyam, plantains, cassava, etc. Going to the farm is something that Yoruba people would delegate as an early morning duty, and the arduous nature of the work implied that it required someone with physical agility. While there is no age restriction of farming, agility is frequently associated with youth. Hence, the proverb is noting how the old person is using their old age to do a task that should have been done while they were younger and stronger.

Second, *Ìgbàyí láàárò l'arúgbó n s'oge*, which translates to (at) this time of the morning, is an old person beautifying herself. The word *s'oge* is a contraction of *se* and *oge*, the former meaning to "do" something and the latter meaning the especially feminine art of beautifying oneself. While *arúgbó* is gender neutral, the context of beautifying oneself is stereotypically feminine in Yoruba culture, thereby making feminine pronouns appropriate in this context. This proverb is a modernized version of the earlier one. The advent of technology has made farming practices not very relatable to the average Yoruba speaker. Beautification however, is still a relevant practice among many Yoruba women. *Oge* by women involves things like hair styling, make-up or fashionable outfits, which are also associated with being young and in one's prime.

Third, *Ìgbàyí láàárò l'arúgbó n k'òkò* which translates to (at) this time of the morning is an old person leaving her husband, is the third and seemingly the most recent of the three expressions of the general phrase *Ìgbàyí láàárò*. *K'òkò* is a contraction of *kò* and *òkò*, which mean

reject/abandon and husband respectively. Again, because the context of this proverb is leaving one's husband at an old age, the appropriate gender to be ascribed to the *arúgbó* is feminine because of the heteronormative nature of Yoruba culture. The simple meaning of this proverb is that it seems pointless for an old woman to leave or divorce her husband because she is already old and has such little time left. This phrase is only meant to highlight the absurdity of doing something at such a late hour. Realistically, there might be justifiable instances where an old woman can leave her husband, such as abuse or life-threatening scenarios. The proverb is not a condonement of abuse of any sort, but rather an illustration of the pointlessness of late decisions. It is the most relatable of the three expressions because its relatability transcends temporal boundaries, making it more universally applicable.

Asides Yoruba cultural values, the Bible provides a foundational framework for understanding what time is. Genesis 1 teaches that time itself is created by God and manifests through day and night and eventual seasonal changes. It also teaches about the ephemeral character of the human life. Ecclesiastes 3:1 emphasizes that “for everything there is a season, and a time for every matter under heaven,” (ESV).⁴ There are also many more verses of the Bible that warn the readers to be conscious of times and seasons and to live purposefully. One must learn that it is not simply about getting a task done, but the timing is an undeniably important factor for gauging the relevance of that task. God on many occasions shows his preference for virtues like hard work and diligence, both of which involve doing things when they should be done. Christian traditions have also recognized this as Catholicism lists slothfulness as one of the seven deadly sins. To illustrate this better, the sons of Issachar were noted in 1 Chronicles 12:32 for understanding the times and knowing what Israel should do, demonstrating the importance of discernment in acting at the right moment. Thus, this paper wants to reflect on the importance of this Yoruba cultural understanding of time and relate it to the Christian theology of time as embedded in Scripture.

1.1 Aim of the Research Work

The aim if this research work is to do a deep reflection on the Yoruba concept of *ìgbàyi láàárò* and examine how it ties with the biblical concept of the passage of time. It aims to prescribe biblically acceptable ways a Christian should think about time and approach the concept of time.

⁴ Except otherwise stated, all scriptural quotations are from the Authorised King James Version of the Holy Bible.

1.2 Research Questions

1. How do humans perceive time?
2. How does God perceive time?
3. What are the differences between God's and the human's perceptions of and approach to time?
4. How does the Yoruba phrase *ìgbà yí láàárò* connect to Christian spirituality and the biblical theology of time?
5. Does human perception of time matter in a spiritual context?

1.3 Research Problem(s)

Although the Bible emphasises the spiritual and moral significance of timing, many Christians struggle to understand how divine timing differs from human perceptions of lateness. At the same time, indigenous cultural expressions, such as the Yoruba phrase *Ìgbà yí láàárò*, reflect how humans experience delays, missed opportunities, and the evaluation of actions according to timing. However, there has been little theological reflection on how such cultural concepts can deepen Christian understanding of the passage of time. This gap raises questions about how believers can integrate such cultural insights with biblical teachings so as to navigate the moral and spiritual implications of timing better in daily life.

1.4 Research Methodology

This research adopts a qualitative, analytical and theological approach to the concept of time perception and its relevance to Christians. It utilises cultural hermeneutics to explore the Yoruba phrase *Ìgbà yí láàárò*, its meaning in its indigenous context and how that meaning is relevant to Christians. It further uses scriptural review and exegesis to analyse passages that are relevant to the phrase *Ìgbà yí láàárò* and how this phrase, alongside its indigenous context, is reflected in the Bible passages. Lastly, it employs a comparative analysis of *chronos* and *kairos* (the two primary distinctions of time in the New Testament), the parallel Yoruba concept of *ìgbà* and *àkókò/àsìkò* as well as the perception of time by God and humans, highlighting the moral and spiritual significance to a believer.

2.0 Scriptural Review and Critical Exegesis

The concept of *Ìgbà yí láàárò* can be seen in several Bible stories. Hence, it is important to review Scripture to give a deeper understanding of the concept of passage of time. The purpose of scriptural review, according to Dele Alaba Ilesanmi (2025), is to develop biblical insights

and bring a deeper understanding and correct interpretation of God's word.⁵ The passages reviewed here show biblical instances where the phrase would be applicable, not necessarily where the phrase was said directly. The passages can be divided into three scenarios: where the phrase was said from a human to another human, from God to a human, and lastly, from a human to God. A clear example of this phrase being said between humans is the story of Jacob vying for his older twin's blessings from their father.

And he said, Is not he rightly named Jacob? for he hath supplanted me these two times: he took away my birthright; and, behold, now he hath taken away my blessing. And he said, Hast thou not reserved a blessing for me? And Isaac answered and said unto Esau, Behold, I have made him thy lord, and all his brethren have I given to him for servants; and with corn and wine have I sustained him: and what shall I do now unto thee, my son? (Gen 27:36-37)

In this context, Esau went ahead to prepare some savoury food for his father, completely unaware that his twin who once bought his birthright has also stolen his blessing. He comes to Isaac expectant but he is met with devastating news; "And when Esau heard the words of his father, he cried with a great and exceeding bitter cry, and said unto his father, Bless me, even me also, O my father" (Gen. 27: 34). In verse 37, Isaac responds to Esau's desperation, saying that he has already given Jacob all the blessings. The original Hebrew *וַיַּעַשׂ* (I have made him) and *וַיִּסְתַּיֵּם* (I have sustained him)⁶ indicate a perfect tense, signifying completion of action. In the ending of the verse, Isaac asks what else he could do for Esau, further highlighting Esau's hopeless situation. This reflects dismissal on Isaac's part; this dismissal was however not done to blame Esau for coming later. It was to show Esau that he had become a victim of an unfortunate heist. The author of Hebrews puts more emphasis on this story where he writes, "... he was rejected (for he found no place of repentance), though he sought it diligently with tears" (Heb. 12:17 ERV). If this story happened in a Yoruba context, the moment Esau requested for his blessing from his father, Isaac could have rightly responded, *ìgbàyí láààrò...*

This phrase being uttered directly by God is not found in the Bible but there are examples that are very close. The most direct example seems to be the voice of Sophia, the feminine

⁵ Ilesanmi, Dele A. "The Imperative of Scriptural Review in Biblical Research Studies: A Proposal for Paradigm Shift from Literature Review" in *International Journal of Biblical Studies*, 2025, vol. 1(1).

⁶ "Genesis 27 Interlinear," *Bible Hub*, <https://biblehub.com/interlinear/genesis/27.htm>

personification of the wisdom of God in Prov 1:20-33. "Then shall they call upon me, but I will not answer; they shall seek me early, but they shall not find me: For that they hated knowledge, and did not choose the fear of the Lord" (Prov. 1:28-29). The English word "early" in this version is translated as "diligently" or "earnestly" from the Hebrew *יִשְׁתַּחֲרָנִי*.⁷ The contexts of the passage shows where Wisdom cries out in the streets, calling for the people to embrace her and condemns the simple who cling to their simplicity; some other versions use naivety, foolishness and ignorance. Wisdom says, because she called and she was refused, and she stretched out her hand and no one regarded (Prov 1:24), she will mock when terror comes (Prov 1:26). The earlier highlighted passage is a continuation of this verse where Wisdom waits for when she will be called upon by those who once rejected her in their folly, and she will reject them as a payback. Therefore, Wisdom shows that there is a time frame within which she expects her call to be responded to. When this time frame passes, and the hour of terror comes, the late-callers will call on her and she will use that time to reject them; a time when she no longer desires to be sought by those who love simplicity. This action is a practical example of *ìgbàyi láàárò*.

In a similar fashion, the bridegroom of Matthew 25: 1-13 tells the foolish virgins that he truly knows them not. The reason for this is that the foolish virgins thought that the best time to begin to look for more oil for their lamps was after they heard the cry at midnight announcing the coming of the bridegroom. The wise virgins were of course not ready to sacrifice some of their extra oil and this prompted the foolish virgins to leave their waiting post to seek the oil that they should have carried from the onset. This made them arrive late to the wedding and the bridegroom said he *truly does not know any of them*. This follows the original Koine Greek, *Ἀμὴν λέγω ὑμῖν, οὐκ οἶδα ὑμᾶς*,⁸ directly translating to "Truly I say to you, I know you not". In this story, there are two instances where it would be appropriate to say *ìgbàyi láàárò*. First is when they started to seek extra oil *after* their lamps were already dying out. The reader of this story could rightly say *ìgbàyi láàárò* to question why the foolish virgins would begin to look for extra oil at such a late hour. The second is when they arrived late to the wedding. One can imagine that the bridegroom would be disappointed in their late coming and would have concluded that they couldn't possibly be part of the guests because the real guests who honour the wedding would have been in the wedding hall. Therefore, seeing the five foolish virgins at the door begging to be let in after the wedding procession has already begun would incite the

⁷ "Proverbs 1 Interlinear," *Bible Hub*, <https://biblehub.com/interlinear/proverbs/1.htm>

⁸ "Matthew 25:12 Interlinear," *Bible Hub*, <https://biblehub.com/interlinear/matthew/25-12.htm>.

bridegroom to say *ìgbàyí láàárò*, with the tone of dismissal. From this parable, it is clear that Jesus implied himself to the bridegroom.

The final category is those who may have said *ìgbàyí láàárò* to God. The, perhaps most fitting, example is Mary and Martha who accused Jesus of coming late. John 11:21 in its original Greek reads "*Κύριε, εἰ ἦς ὧδε, οὐκ ἂν ἀπέθανεν ὁ ἀδελφός μου*"⁹ which translates to "Lord if you had been here, my brother would not have died", the exact statement Mary made when she met Jesus (v.32). The statement shows both Martha and Mary telling Jesus that he came outside the time frame of when their brother would have been conveniently healed. The following verse reads "But I know, that even now, whatsoever thou wilt ask of God, God will give it thee" (John 11:22); this shows that Martha still had some hope in Jesus even though Jesus came later than she would have preferred. If she wanted to be rude to Jesus, she could have, upon seeing him, said *ìgbàyí láàárò*, signaling to Jesus that his miracle is late but may be reluctantly accepted.

3.0 Theo-Theoretical and Conceptual Frameworks

3.1. The Concept of Time

Time is how humans count and measure moments. Time is a very complex concept, but it is fundamental to our understanding of life and living. Seasons come in cycles, days come in days and nights, the earth rotates around its axis and gives a full day, a complete rotation around the sun gives the measurement of a year, and there are many other examples of how we experience time in motion. This goes to show that time has a structure that we as humans can respond to. Aside from this, humans have developed ways to calculate and measure time. Humans invented calendars and mechanical clocks, rely on astronomical events like earth and moon rotation cycles to determine events, and think of time in the past, present, and future senses. This literal usage of time is known as the denotative usage.

Another way time is referenced is the connotative use. This usage gives time a meaning that is beyond mere literal or measurable meaning. An example of this is how "morning" may suggest youth, new beginnings, "tomorrow" may be used to refer to the future rather than the following day. On a deeper level, it refers to how societies interpret or experience time. The early morning hours may be associated with peace, readiness or productivity, which is why it makes sense to say *ìgbàyí láàárò* as an indication of a late action. Culture and tradition shapes how people

⁹ "John 11:21 Interlinear," *Bible Hub*, <https://biblehub.com/interlinear/john/11-21.htm>

experience and interpret time, as well as the value they ascribe to it. We have also attached cultural significance to timing, which is why the phrase *ìgbàyí láàárò* can be so culturally significant. In summary, time is simply the life we live and how we live it.

A third usage of time may be the figurative use, which uses "time" as a metaphor for expressing a larger concept. It represents ideas like growth, judgment, destiny, or divine purpose. For example, "harvest time" may symbolise a reward or consequences, and "the end time" may represent judgment rather than a specific date on a calendar or an emotional association of time with a cultural value. In this usage, time carries theological or philosophical weight at a deeper level than the connotative usage, which still refers to real and measurable moments with social significance.

3.2.0 Fundamental Dimensions of Time

3.2.1 Time in Physics

"Physicists define time as the progression of events from the past to the present into the future".¹⁰ With this simple definition, there are many aspects which physicists study to make sense of the concept of time. Physics asks questions like why time is irreversible and the general and special relativity of time where time may behave differently depending the "frame of reference of an observer".¹¹ The possibility of time travel, time perception and the question of if there will ever be an end of time are also concerning topics in Physics.

From this perspective, time is only studied to be understood as a concept. It does not deal with the meaning it may have to people and societies nor the emotional weight it may carry for different people.

3.2.2 Time in Biology

"Your biological clock is ticking" is a phrase that many men and women have heard at different points of their life. The origin of this phrase lies in the fundamental passing of how a person's body counts time; in another word, aging. "The ticks of a human being's biological clock are produced by heartbeats, the rhythm of breathing, cycles of sleeping and waking, and periodic menstruation, although there is no conscious counting of the cycles."¹² This clock keeps ticking

¹⁰ "What Is Time? A Simple Explanation," *ThoughtCo*, <https://www.thoughtco.com/what-is-time-4156799>

¹¹ "What Is Time? A Simple Explanation,"

¹² "Time," *Internet Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, <https://iep.utm.edu/time/#H2>

even in the absence of mechanical clocks; it doesn't stop even when one is unable to observe the natural passage of time through seasons and cycles.

This dimension of time does not fully rely on day and night cycles or seasonal cycles. Rather, it relies on "factors such as your habits, your age, and chemical changes taking place in your body." It is not stable like the mechanical clocks but dependent on many abstract variables.

3.2.3 Time in Psychology

Psychological time is the reason the sentence "Your biological clock is ticking" can have such a traumatic effect on the hearer. The ticking of the biological clock signals that one is approaching the end of a time frame where some biological goals may not be attainable. It could be childbirth or pregnancy, fitness goals or any other thing that requires the agility of youth. What makes the statement so impactful is how the passage of the biological clock makes people *feel*.

"Psychological time is the subjective experience of past, present, and future that shapes how we perceive ourselves and our possibilities...".¹³ The keyword in this definition is subjective. Psychological time is dependent on individuals and not necessarily a shared phenomenon. This is connected to why many people *feel* January is significantly slower than all the other months, even though this is the same literal 24 hours and 31 days. It is shared because many people agree with that feeling but individualistic those who agree still experience the speed relatively. Some may say it's a bit slow while others feel it is excruciatingly slow. There are still those who feel that the month is in fact moving very fast while some remain neutral. This reflects the diversity in psychological time. It also shows that psychological time can also be seen in the emotions and value associated with events. This is why things like earliness and lateness can be a big deal for cultures and societies. There are time frames within which the culture thinks something should be done, anything outside of that might be responded to negatively.

All of this easily connects to the phrase *ìgbàyí láàárò*. An emotional tone usually accompanies the phrase. It could be disappointment, dismissal, reluctance, hopefulness, anger, sadness or pain. It all connects to how person has psychologically experienced the time which was lost, and this experience birthed the response *ìgbàyí láàárò*.

3.2.4 Time in Theology / The Bible

¹³ "Psychological Time: How We Create Our Own Reality," Human Performance, <https://humanperformance.ie/psychological-time/>

All the above examples can be found in the Bible but the Bible also lays foundations of what a Christian should understand about time in relation to God, humanity and Christianity. The first is that God is not time-bound unlike humans and other created things. Gen. 1:2 mentions the spirit of God hovering over the waters before the formation of the earth *before* the cycle of day and night was then created on the first day. God created time and is therefore above it, no matter how incomprehensible that may sound. 2 Peter 3:8 mentions how "...that one day is with the Lord as a thousand years, and a thousand years as one day," showing that God perceives time very differently from humans. Habakkuk also shows that God, like humans, acts at appointed times.

There are several examples of instances where timing mattered, besides the ones examined in scriptural review section above. The Bible often shows that timing matters in a person's response to God. In 1 Samuel 13, Saul acted too early by offering a sacrifice before Samuel arrived, and this mistake cost him God's approval as king. In Luke 19:41–44, Jesus mourns over Jerusalem because the people failed to recognize the moment when God came to them, leading to loss instead of peace. Another example appears in John 7:6, where Jesus explains that his actions must happen at the right time, showing that even obedience must align with proper timing. These passages suggest that in the Bible, delay, haste, or missed moments can all affect spiritual outcomes.

3.3.0 Cultural Meaning of *Ìgbàyi láàárò*

The phrase *ìgbàyi láàárò* is one that readily comes to the lips of Yoruba speakers, particularly when they are presented with a favour or requested task that is perceived as coming too late. *Ìgbàyi láàárò* literally means "(at) this time of the morning". Many cultures associate early mornings with productivity, as it is the start of the day. Therefore, when a Yoruba person asks for a favour or demands that a task be done, there is an expected time frame where that favour or task would still be relevant. If it is done outside that time frame, the person to whom the task was given should expect to hear *ìgbàyi láàárò*. Since early mornings are often associated with productivity in many cultures of the world, the late task or favour is akin to something that should have been done since the early hours of the morning. This example is most relevant to earlier societies that were primarily agricultural and rural. The farmers of the communities would have gone to their respective farms as early as around 6am. If a person wakes up later than usual and decides they want to head for the farm at the time of the day where the sun is

risen and the weather is significantly hotter, say around 11am, a family member might comment *ìgbàyi láàárò*, insinuating that the farmer has missed the most productive window.

In the earlier example, the family member who said *ìgbàyi láàárò* was simply commenting on the lateness of the farmer. This is a common context in which the phrase is used; as a comment on a third party's lateness. However, regarding tasks or favours demanded by a person, the one who says *ìgbàyi láàárò* generally expresses two tones, and even in humorous contexts, these tones remain evident however faintly. The first tone is reluctance and the second is dismissal. The first tone can be seen in the example of a person who needs help cleaning their room and they ask a friend for this help. Say the friend comes in when the person is almost done cleaning, they could say to the friend *ìgbàyi láàárò*, expressing their disappointment but still allowing the friend to help out with the little work that is left of the cleaning.

Dismissal can be seen in the event where a young person has been told by the parent to buy ingredients needed to make the family's lunch but they decide to leave for the market in the evening. The young person could come out of their room and meet the parent already making said lunch with the ingredients that they should have bought earlier in the day. The parent could say *ìgbàyi láàárò*, implying that they no longer need the help of the young person in buying the ingredients. This dismissal works for when the help or task is no longer needed and also when it is no longer wanted, even if it is needed. In the earlier example, the person cleaning the room could say to the friend *ìgbàyi láàárò* and decide that they do not want any help from the friend anymore even though there could be some things the friend could still help with. Both tones could also reflect in the humorous uses of *ìgbàyi láàárò*.

While *ìgbàyi láàárò* is a phrase commonly used, there are many instances where this phrase may technically be applicable but socially inappropriate to express. For example, a person could travel a very long distance to give their friend a surprise birthday gift. Say in the process, they missed the friend's birthday, it might be insensitive of the friend to say *ìgbàyi láàárò* considering the efforts and inevitable delay that the person faced. It would only be appropriate if it is said with some humour that is understandable by the traveller.

In conclusion, *ìgbàyi láàárò* is a phrase that expresses social judgment about lateness, showing that something done late can lose its value or relevance. The fact that it is relational shows that it is purely a product of psychological time; the subjective way in which people attribute importance and value to the passage of time.

3.4.0. Theological Meaning of *Ìgbàyi láàárò*

While *ìgbàyí láàárò* culturally communicates that a favour or action has arrived too late, the phrase can also serve as a perspective for understanding human responsibility, divine timing, and the moral weight of time-based opportunities. In theology, *ìgbàyí láàárò* reminds believers that timing is not merely functional or practical, but also deeply spiritual and morally significant.

First, timing in the Bible as an expression of divine "order". The Bible emphasises that there is a proper time (or an appropriate time frame) for every action under heaven. Ecclesiastes 3:1–8 states: “To every thing there is a season, and a time to every purpose under the heaven: a time to be born, and a time to die; a time to plant, and a time to pluck up that which is planted...” This passage demonstrates that time is methodical and also purposeful, both in the natural and moral sense. Similarly, Ecclesiastes 12:1 admonishes readers to “Remember now thy Creator in the days of thy youth, while the evil days come not, nor the years draw nigh, when thou shalt say, I have no pleasure in them.” This verse demonstrates the urgency of remembering and obeying God since it is tied to human mortality and the limited time we have to respond to God. Therefore, old age would be outside the preferred appropriate and productive time frame to remember and serve God. *Ìgbàyí láàárò* resonates with this theme because it emphasises that delayed actions *can* lose significance if they fall outside their appropriate “time.”

Another theological significance of *ìgbàyí láàárò* is the human experience of discouragement that comes perceived lateness of favours and opportunities. A theological application of *ìgbàyí láàárò* shows that Bible characters often feel frustration, disappointment, or discouragement when help, blessing, or response arrives later than they would prefer. Some of the Davidic Psalms also reflect this emotional reality. David cries “How long, O Lord? will thou forget me for ever? how long wilt thou hide thy face from me? How long shall I take counsel in my soul, having sorrow in my heart daily?” (Psalm 13:1–2). This cry shows his psychological perception of the period of sorrow he is in. He *feels* that he has suffered for too long but he still shows desperation to be saved. David showed hope and appreciated God's salvation, whether it came "late" or not. A more appropriate example would be Mary the sister of Martha whose brother died, as explained in 2.0.

In a similar fashion, actions of lateness can lead to severe spiritual consequences. In Luke 19:41–44, Jesus weeps over Jerusalem because the city failed to recognize “the time of her visitation,” leading to loss rather than blessing. So, in the same way the Yoruba phrase *ìgbàyí*

láàárò conveys that a favour “comes too late,” the Bible shows that delayed human response can have tangible spiritual consequences.

It has been established that God himself is not bound by time like humans are. Yet, even though God is not constrained by human clocks, He still acts within a divinely appointed timing and according to purpose. Paul illustrates this saying, “But when the fulness of the time was come, God sent forth his Son, made of a woman, made under the law.” (Gal. 4:4). Again, Jesus said to his disciples, “...It is not for you to know the times or the seasons, which the Father hath put in his own power” (Acts 1:7). This illustrates that God has appointed times and seasons in which he operates and it is not for humans to know and monitor. Therefore, God’s timing is not arbitrary; it is purposeful, meaningful. This connects with *ìgbàyí láàárò* because human limitations in thinking may push one to conclude that God is late in giving a favour. Sarah laughed at God when the angels said she will have a son, knowing that she was past her biological productive window. To her, the miracle she spent so long hoping for was already late. However, remembering passages like Acts 1:7 reminds us that how we feel about the passage of time is irrelevant because psychological and biological times are for us to experience while God's timing is the superior standard which we may not know.

Finally, the theological importance of *ìgbàyí láàárò* lies in its demonstration that time carries moral and spiritual weight. As timing is important in cultures, whereby wrong timing may warrant in *ìgbàyí láàárò*, timing is also important in spirituality, for both God and humans.

The Bridge

Ìgbàyí láàárò from cultural and theological lenses serves as a bridge between everyday human experiences, cultural understanding, and theological reflection. Both the Bible and Yoruba thought distinguish between time as **sequence** and time as **significance**, and *ìgbàyí láàárò* operates within the second category. The New Testament distinguishes between two primary understandings of time: *chronos* (χρόνος) and *kairos* (καιρός) which parallel to two ways Yoruba language qualifies time. *Chronos* refers to the measurable and sequential aspect of time, that is, time as a duration or length while *kairos* refers to a season or opportunity; a time that has been assigned meaning, urgency, and responsibility. *Chronos* parallels with *àkókò/ásìkò* while *kairos* parallels with *ìgbà*. Both words literally mean time but are used in different contexts. Both *chronos* and *àkókò* refer to moments or measurable time like years and seconds and *kairos* and *ìgbà* refer to decisive times or seasons. This parallelism is however

not strict. The Yoruba words may occasionally be used interchangeably. As mentioned earlier, it is usually dependent on context.

In Acts 1:6-7, Jesus responds to his disciples' question about timing, saying “It is not for you to know the **times** or the seasons...”; the Greek word used is χρόνος (*chronos*). Here, *chronos* refers to measurable periods known only to God. On the other hand, in Luke 19:44, “...because you did not know the **time** of your visitation” uses the Greek καιρὸν (*kairon*). This verse directly links *kairos* with missed opportunity which fits the *ìgbàyi láàárò* theme. *Chronos* defines time as **sequence** while *kairos* defines time as **significance**; *ìgbàyi láàárò* also defines time as **significance**.

5.0 Findings

This study finds that:

1. Timing in Scripture is more than a measure of hours or days; it carries profound moral and spiritual significance, particularly in moments of repentance and obedience. Acting at the right time is often linked to faithfulness, diligence, and aligning oneself with God’s purposes.
2. In the Yoruba context, the expression *Ìgbàyi láàárò* is an understanding of time that also goes beyond mere chronology. It emphasizes that there are right moments to act and that discernment of these moments matters.
3. The analysis reveals that human psychological experiences of delay often produce discouragement, and this is what cultural expressions like *Ìgbàyi láàárò* reflect.
4. From a theological perspective, the distinction between *chronos* (measured time) and *kairos* (opportune, divinely appointed time) helps to explain why delayed action may result in missed spiritual opportunities.
5. Although God is not bound by time, the Bible consistently shows that even divine actions happen within appointed moments. This consistent behavior of God is an indication of the divine expectations of how humans should approach the concept of timing. It teaches that acting timely is also as important as the action itself.
6. Lastly, this study shows that indigenous cultural concepts like *Ìgbàyi láàárò* can serve as valid tools for interpreting biblical and theological themes of time and response. Theological reflection grounded in local language and culture can deepen Christian understanding of abstract doctrines.

7. The study teaches that Christians must think about time not only as "clock" time, but as a moral and spiritual responsibility, because lateness sometimes has spiritual consequences.

6.0 Recommendation

1. This reflection provides several recommendations for individual believers. Unlike the cultural understanding of *ìgbàyí láàárò*, God's lateness is more relevant. When Sarah laughed at the lateness of her miracle, the son she bore did not reduce the significance of her promise to become the mother of nations. Hence, if she had a son in her youth, it would not have turned out any more significant than she having a son in her old age. This is a classic example of God choosing to do something in His own timing but the humans are affected by their own psychological perception of time.
2. God can say *ìgbàyí láàárò* to a person but not necessarily verbally. It has been shown that God also prioritises tasks being done at an appropriate time. When that window passes, *ìgbàyí láàárò* would be appropriate to say. If one then asks, what then is the place of mercy, forgiveness and other timeless attributes of God? Even though Ps 136 teaches that God's mercy endures forever, even those timeless attributes will "end" one day for those who refuse to operate in accordance with His timing. This is the reason for the existence of Hell. Hell is for those who received mercy but refused to channel the acceptance of that mercy into productivity for him during the time frame God gave them, i.e their lifetime. The parable of the ten virgins and the parable of the rich man express this too. There will be a time where it will be too late to do whatever for God anymore. If anyone in Hell therefore tries to ask God for mercy, God may respond with *ìgbàyí láàárò*. The realization of this would quicken a Christian's consciousness of *kairos*. Therefore, timing (*kairos*) is a responsibility of a Christian so that their spirituality does not suffer from repeated comments of *ìgbàyí láàárò* from God, figuratively speaking.
3. A Christian is better off reinterpreting time to fit God's flexible understanding of time. A good demonstrator of this was Ezekiel who replied, "Sovereign Lord, you alone know" when he was asked if dry bones could come back to life (Ez. 37:3). He believed their biological clock was done ticking but he decided to show trust in God's abilities. This was the same attitude of Martha in John 11:21. One should remember that this type of time is psychological and not determinant in any way of God's timing. To defeat the constraints of psychological time in a believer's walk with God, they must adopt a flexible understanding of time while realizing that *ìgbàyí láàárò* can and should never be applicable to God.

4. Christians must treat time, both the denotative, connotative and figurative kinds as a faith-based matter. With the level of importance that God places on timing, as shown in this study, timing must be approached as a spiritual discipline. A believer must be mindful of timing in the context of ordinary social events, as well the grand scheme of God's *kairos*. "Time is a priceless treasure or an inestimable jewel given by God to humanity... Our lives are governed by time. God made it so".¹⁴
5. Lastly, Christians must be reminded that wasting time undermines both discipline and spiritual growth. When time is wasted, it reflects a lack of self-control and reduces opportunities for spiritual development, service, and obedience. A careless attitude toward time can weaken a believer's commitment to God. Therefore, Christians must realize that they are called to use their time wisely; recognising how they spend it is part of their responsibility to God.

7.0 Conclusion

The study of *Ìgbàyi láàárò* shows that both culture and faith give deep meaning to timing. While humans often feel discouraged when help comes late, God's timing is always purposeful and effective. Integrating cultural insights with Scripture highlights the moral and spiritual importance of acting at the right moment. Understanding this helps believers trust God's plan and recognise the significance of timely responses in life. Furthermore, this study shows that time is not just something neutral or mechanical but something shaped by culture, theology, and everyday human experiences. As scholars such as John S. Mbiti have observed, time is often understood through actual experiences and events with a shared communal meaning rather than an abstract measurement. This also shows that being sensitive to timing is important for both social harmony and spiritual growth. Hence, a proper understanding of timing, as seen in both cultural practice and biblical teaching, provides a fuller way of understanding human actions and divine activity. In the light of all these insights, this paper will therefore contribute to the expansion of the frontiers of knowledge in theological studies.

¹⁴ "Keeping to Time," *Christopress*, <https://www.christopress.com/keeping-to-time/>

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